

Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Mn(II) Complexes of *bis*-Quinolyl Hydrazone of Biacetal

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$[M(BQHBA)X_2]$ ($M = \text{Cu(II)}, \text{Ni(II)}, \text{Mn(II)}$ and $X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{SCN}^-$); $[M(BQHBA)ClO_4]ClO_4$ ($M = \text{Cu(II)}, \text{Ni(II)}$); $[\text{Co(II)}(BQHBA)]X_2$ ($X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{SCN}^-$) and $[\text{Co(II)}(BQHBA)ClO_4](ClO_4)_2$ type complexes have been isolated and characterized by elemental analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility measurements and electronic and ir spectra. Octahedral structure is assigned to copper(II), nickel(II), manganese(II) and cobalt(II) complexes while cobalt(II) complexes are tetrahedral.

THE mono and *bis* heterocyclic hydrazones with carbonyl and diketones have been explored as potential multidentate ligands and their transition metal complexes have been studied by various physico-chemical techniques to know about their electronic structures¹⁻¹⁹. *Bis*quinolylhydrazone of

biacetal (BQHBA) (I) is a newly synthesized ligand belonging to this class and has been chosen to study the steric effect on the geometry of the complexes which are expected in changing the pyridine ring by more bulky quinoline ring. The present communication describes the characterization of the copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II) and manganese(II) complexes of BQHBA by magnetic susceptibility and conductance measurements and electronic and ir spectra.

Preparation of BQHBA :

*Bis*quinolylhydrazone of biacetal was prepared by mixing 2-hydrazinoquinoline and biacetal in 2 : 1 mole ratio in alcohol. The resulting solution was treated with 6 ml glacial acetic acid. The dark red solution so obtained was cooled in ice water when bright yellow compound separated out which was filtered, washed successively with alcohol and acetone and recrystallized from alcohol. (Found : C, 71.61 ; N, 22.61 ; H, 5.30. Calcd. ; C, 71.74 ; N, 22.83 ; H, 5.43%). The compound melts at 268° without decomposition.

Preparation of the complexes :

$[M(BQHBA)X_2]$ ($X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{SCN}^-$ and $M = \text{Cu(II)}, \text{Ni(II)}$ and Mn(II)) and $[\text{Co(II)}(BQHBA)]X_2$ type complexes could be easily

prepared by mixing the appropriate metal salts and the ligand in equimolar ratio in DMF. In each case, the complexes get precipitated which are filtered, washed and dried over silica gel in a vacuum desiccator.

$[M(BQHBA)X]X$ ($X = \text{ClO}_4^-$ and $M = \text{Cu(II)}, \text{Ni(II)}$) and $[\text{Co(III)}(BQHBA)ClO_4](ClO_4)_2$ type complexes were prepared by mixing the appropriate metal perchlorate and the ligand in equimolar ratio in DMF. The resulting solution was concentrated by distilling excess of the solvent under reduced pressure. The complexes separated out in each case, which were filtered and washed with water and alcohol successively and dried over P_4O_{10} in a vacuum desiccator.

Physical measurements :

Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out at room temperature on a Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ as the calibrant. The conductance was measured in DMF solution (0.001 M). The absorption spectra were recorded on DMR-21 spectrophotometer in nujol mull and ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 621 Grating ir spectrophotometer in KBr pellets.

Results and Discussion

The results of conductance, elemental analysis and magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes are presented in Table 1.

The nmr spectrum of BQHBA recorded in a mixture of CDCl_3 and TFA shows the methyl protons appearing as a singlet absorption at 2.5 ppm due to the highly symmetrical structure of the molecule. The aromatic protons appear as multiplet in the range 7-8.5 ppm. The intensity of this multiplet corresponds to 12 protons present on the two quinoline rings. NH protons could not be located due to the presence of the TFA in the solvent mixture.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND CONDUCTANCE DATA

Compound	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				\bar{X}	μ_{eff} (B.M.) at RT	Δ (DMF) mho $\text{cm}^{-1} \cdot \text{mole}^{-1}$
	Metal	Carbon	Nitrogen	Hydrogen			
[Cu(BQHBA)Cl ₂]	12.31 (12.64)	52.41 (52.53)	16.71 (16.71)	3.67 (3.98)	14.02 (14.13)	1.68	—
[Cu(BQHBA)(ClO ₄) ₂]	9.87 (10.07)	41.73 (41.87)	13.10 (13.32)	3.01 (3.17)	—	1.73	85.47
[Ni(BQHBA)Cl ₂]	11.56 (11.79)	52.89 (53.04)	16.76 (16.87)	3.91 (4.02)	14.01 (14.26)	3.04	—
[Ni(BQHBA)Br ₂]	9.72 (10.01)	44.91 (45.01)	14.19 (14.32)	3.17 (3.41)	27.03 (27.24)	2.90	—
[Ni(BQHBA)(SCN) ₂]	10.75 (10.82)	48.43 (48.64)	15.32 (15.48)	3.43 (3.68)	—	2.93	—
[Ni(BQHBA)(ClO ₄) ₂]	9.28 (9.38)	42.01 (42.19)	13.19 (13.42)	3.01 (3.19)	—	2.98	90.03
[Co(BQHBA)Cl ₂]	11.78 (11.83)	52.95 (53.02)	16.56 (16.87)	3.91 (4.02)	14.18 (14.26)	4.32	160.34
[Co(BQHBA)Br ₂]	9.75 (10.08)	44.63 (44.91)	14.03 (14.39)	3.18 (3.40)	26.89 (27.19)	4.63	150.14
[Co(BQHBA)(SCN) ₂]	10.73 (10.86)	48.43 (48.62)	15.38 (15.47)	3.51 (3.68)	—	4.63	143.28
[Co(BQHBA)(ClO ₄) ₂]	7.93 (8.12)	36.12 (36.89)	11.41 (11.58)	2.61 (2.75)	—	Di _h	150.43
[Mn(BQHBA)Cl]	10.95 (11.12)	53.34 (53.44)	16.86 (17.00)	3.83 (4.05)	14.21 (14.37)	6.06	—

The mass spectrum of the compound shows the parent peak at m/e 368 which corresponds to the molecular weight. Another significant peak observed is at $m/e=184$ which results from the parent mole-

cular ion through the rupture of C-C bond. The appearance of this molecular ion also accounts for the symmetry of the molecule around O-O bond. The mass spectral data have only been used to establish the formation of the bisquinolyldiazene and not monoquinolyldiazene during the condensation reaction.

Except [M(BQHBA)ClO₄]₂ [M=Ni(II), Cu(II)] and [Co(III)(BQHBA)ClO₄](ClO₄)₂, and [Co(II)(BQHBA)]X₂ which are 1:1 and 1:2 electrolytes respectively, all other complexes are of non-electrolytic nature and supports the presence of the halide and thiocyanate ions in the coordination sphere. The elemental analysis of all the compounds under study correspond to 1:1 metal:ligand ratio.

The magnetic moments for the copper(II) complexes are very near to μ_{SO} for copper(II) compounds which behave as normal paramagnetic. In view of the tetradentate character of the ligand, elemental analysis and conductance measurements,

the complexes could possibly be octahedral. The bidentate character²⁰⁻²⁴ of ClO₄⁻ in the complex is supported by the splitting of ν_3 band of ClO₄ owing to C_{2v} symmetry into three bands appearing at 1140, 1110 and 1088 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum of the compound (Fig. 1). The mull absorption spectra of the compounds show broad absorption at 14290 and 11760 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ and characteristic of Oh geometry. Due to the low symmetry in [Cu(II)(BQHBA)Cl₂], ${}^3T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ appears as a split band at 10260 and 14290 cm^{-1} .

While [Ni(BQHBA)₂X₂] (X=Cl⁻, Br⁻, SCN⁻) are non-electrolytes, Ni(BQHBA)(ClO₄)₂ is 1:1 electrolyte which indicates the placement of one of the ClO₄⁻ to be inside the coordination sphere. The ir spectra of the compound also show ν_3 band appearing in the form of a group of three at 1145, 1110 and 1085 cm^{-1} which demands the bidentate character of the perchlorate anion. Keeping in view the elemental analysis and the conductance data and tetradentate and planarity character of the ligand, octahedral structure could be assigned to all the nickel(II) complexes which is supported by the magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectral data. All the complexes have magnetic moments at room temperature very near to $\mu_{\text{so}}=2.90$ B.M. Octahedral nickel(II) complexes have magnetic moments ranging from 2.9 to 3.4 B.M. depending upon the contribution of orbital momentum, and this contribution in the present case seems to be very small.

Higher energy d-d bands which either appear in T_{2g} or Oh geometries, will be obscured by the high intensity L-L* charge transfer bands appearing in the complexes but only the d-d bands expected in the near infrared region may appear in the absorption spectra. All the planar nickel(II) complexes

Fig. 1. Splitting of ν_3 band of ClO_4^- .

give absorption spectral bands only below 10000 cm^{-1} , and tetrahedral nickel(II) complexes yield spectral bands below 8000 cm^{-1} . The nickel(II) complexes under study have spectral bands in the range $10000\text{--}5830\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are the characteristic bands of Oh geometry and supports the conclusion derived on the basis of the susceptibility data. The assignments of the spectral bands are presented in Table 2.

$\text{Co}(\text{BQHBA})(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ is diamagnetic and hence the complex is a cobalt(III) compound with octahedral structure. The conductance of the compound in DMF corresponds to 1 : 2 electrolyte and this fixes one of the perchlorate anion to be in the coordination sphere. As ν_3 band of perchlorate group also appears as a band split (Fig. 1) into three at $1140, 1115$ and 1075 cm^{-1} , perchlorate anion in the coordination sphere acts as bidentate so as to give octahedral geometry for the complex in view of tetradentate nature of the chelating molecule.

$[\text{Co}(\text{II})(\text{BQHBA})]\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{SCN}^-$) complexes have molar conductance (DMF) in the range $140\text{--}170\text{ mho cm}^{-1}\text{ mole}^{-1}$ which confirms them to

be 1 : 2 type electrolytes and hence the anions could be placed in the outer sphere. For tetrahedral Co^{2+} , the ${}^4\text{T}_1$ and ${}^4\text{T}_2$ states are mixed into the ground state under the action of the spin-orbit coupling and $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2\left(-1 - \frac{4\lambda}{10Dq}\right)[S(S+1)]^{1/2}$ B.M. and experimental values for the magnetic moment lie in the range 4.4-4.7 B.M. However, in octahedral field, the ground state, ${}^4\text{T}_1$, is orbitally degenerate and causes an orbital angular momentum contribution to the magnetic moment. The moment lies between the limits of spin-only, $\mu_{\text{eff}}^{\text{SO}} = [4S(S+1)]^{1/2} = 3.88$ B.M. and $\mu = [4S(S+1) + L(L+1)]^{1/2} = 5.2$ B.M. where S is the total spin angular momentum of $(3/2)\frac{1}{2}$ and L is the total orbital angular momentum of $3\frac{1}{2}$. The actual value depends upon the amount of L remaining associated with the ground state orbital triplet and the experimental values usually lie in the range 4.7-5.2 B.M.

Since most of the planar cobalt(II) are of low-spin type, tetrahedral geometry could be proposed for the cobalt(II) complexes under study in view of the room temperature values of the magnetic moments which lie in the 4.4-4.7 B.M. range and gets a support from the electronic spectra.

From the energy level diagram shown above for tetrahedral d^7 , it is obvious that such systems should exhibit three transitions from ground state ${}^4\text{A}_2$ to the higher excited states. As ν_1 is rarely observed and the band corresponding to ν_2 [${}^4\text{A}_2 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{F})$] is usually broad and appears in near infrared, ν_3 [${}^4\text{A}_2 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{P})$] is quite intense, broad and exhibits a great deal of structure and usually the fine structure of ν_3 , which is not observed in the case of octahedral geometry, could be taken as a qualitative measure for assigning tetrahedral geometry to the complex since $[\text{Co}(\text{III})(\text{BQHBA})\text{ClO}_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$, which

TABLE 2 - ASSIGNMENTS OF ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS

X	$[\text{Cu}(\text{II})(\text{BQHBA})\text{X}]$	$[\text{Ni}(\text{II})(\text{BQHBA})\text{X}_2]$		$[\text{Co}(\text{II})(\text{BQHBA})\text{X}_2]$	${}^4\text{A}_2(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{P})$
	${}^3\text{T}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{E}_g (\text{cm}^{-1})$	${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}$	${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$	${}^4\text{A}_2 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{F})$	
-Cl	10260, 14300	8340	18520	7690	14900, 17400, 20000
-ClO ₄	11760	9090*	16850*	8000#	
-Br		9090	16000	8000	15400, 18200, 22220
-SCN		6900, 9090	17540	8200	16700, 18200

* $[\text{Ni}(\text{II})(\text{BQHBA})\text{ClO}_4]\text{ClO}_4$

$[\text{Co}(\text{II})(\text{BQHBA})(\text{ClO}_4)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$

is octahedral, does not show the fine structure of ν_3 band. $[\text{Mn}(\text{BQHBA})\text{Cl}_2]$ is also non-electrolyte and the magnetic moment for the complex is 6.06 B.M. which confirms s ground state for manganese(II) in the complex. The d-d spectral bands for the compound are completely obscured by the L-L* charge transfer bands.

In $[\text{M}(\text{II})(\text{BQHBA})(\text{SCN})_2]$ ($\text{M}=\text{Cu}, \text{Ni}$), from the positions of the $\nu(\text{CN})$, $\nu(\text{CS})$ and $\nu(\text{NCS})$ bands given in Table 3, it is obvious that SCN group in all the cases coordinates to the metal as isothiocyanato $^{2-}$ and not thiocyanate form as is expected with 3d transition metal ions in which coordination to the metal takes place through nitrogen of SCN group.

TABLE 3—VIBRATIONAL FREQUENCIES OF SON CONTAINING COMPLEXES

Compound	$\nu(\text{CN})$	$\nu(\text{CS})$	$\delta(\text{NCS})$
$[\text{Cu}(\text{BQHBA})(\text{SCN})_2]$	2030	824	450, 470
$[\text{Ni}(\text{BQHBA})(\text{SCN})_2]$	2035	830	480, 502

In all the complexes, $\nu(\text{NH})$ either retains its position or due to complexation, appears as split band. This supports that hydrazinic protons do not undergo deprotonation as a result of complexation. $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ also appear as band of medium intensity in all the complexes along with $\nu(\text{M}-\text{X})$ in the same region. Since the ligand also shows absorption in the same region, definite assignments of these bands were not possible.

Now we discuss the results of ESR spectral studies carried out on copper(II) compounds in DMF solution both at room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature (frozen state). The spectra are shown

in Figs. 2 and 3. Unfortunately, due to the low solubility of the compounds, good spectra could not be obtained. Superhyperfine splitting due to nitrogens was also not observed. At room temperature, the solution spectrum is indicative of the splitting due to copper hyperfine and is isotropic. However, in frozen state the spectra are anisotropic and shows the splitting due to copper hyperfine both in g_{\perp} and g_{\parallel} . ESR parameters which have been calculated are presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4—ESR PARAMETERS FOR THE COPPER(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	Temp.	g_{iso}	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A (gauss)	
					A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}
$[\text{Cu}(\text{BQHBA})\text{Cl}_2]$	RT	2.155			115	15
	DMF					
	LNT					
$[\text{Cu}(\text{BQHBA})\text{ClO}_4]$	RT	2.150				
	DMF					
	LNT					

A_{Cu} (115 G) calculated from the frozen DMF solution spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{BQHBA})\text{Cl}_2]$ is substantially low and the magnitude rules out the possibility of either square or octahedral arrangement of the ligands in the compounds both of which yield A_{Cu} in the range 180-200 $\text{G}^{29,30}$. It favours a tetrahedral geometry in the complex which could result possibly from the dissociation of the complex in DMF or from the non-coordinating nature of two of the nitrogens. The former is more supporting as the complex has been assigned octahedral structure in

Fig. 2. ESR spectra at RT (DMF Soln.).
A. $[\text{Cu}(\text{II})(\text{BQHBA})\text{Cl}_2]$; B. $[\text{Cu}(\text{II})(\text{BQHBA})\text{ClO}_4]$

Fig. 3. ESR spectra at LNT (DMF soln., Frozen).

A. $[\text{Cu}(\text{II})(\text{BQBHA})\text{ClO}_4]\text{ClO}_4$; B. $[\text{Cu}(\text{II})(\text{BQBHA})\text{Cl}_2]$

solid state from electronic and ir spectral data as discussed earlier. The resolution in the spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{BQHBA})\text{ClO}_4]\text{ClO}_4$ was very poor and the four lines due to splitting in g_{\parallel} were not observed clearly. Only the more intense signal corresponding to g_{\perp} was observed. But from the magnitude of g_{iso} and g_{\perp} , which are comparable with those of $[\text{Cu}(\text{BQHBA})\text{Cl}_2]$, it could be concluded that the two compounds have identical behaviour.

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